

DIVISION BY ZERO BOTTOM LINE

ANSWERED

BY

DAVID N. KATHURI

ABOUT

My (earliest) answers to Division by Zero questions in Quora Forums.

The Future and Past are Void

a) Future:

If time is slowed and yours isn't, your time will be faster than other people's time; therefore your time will be in the future of other people's/matter's time.

If you move, you'll leave vacuum because it will take a longer time for air or any other matter to fill your space because its time has been slowed; hence the future is void.

b) Past:

If time is stopped and yours isn't, the time of every matter, will be in the past because their time has been stopped.

If you move, you'll leave vacuum because no air or any other matter will fill your space because its time has been stopped; hence the past is void also.

Proving that Past and Future are Vacuum

i. Past:

When an object is moved from point A to B, point A becomes the past of point B because the object was (= past) in Point A and now (= present) is in point B; but point A is vacuum unless air or any other matter fills its space. This is because when the object moved from point A, an empty space (= vacuum) was formed (unless air or other matter fills this space).

(nb Time = Distance/Speed)

ii. Future:

When one expects an object to move from point A to B, the object doesn't move to point B because it's just an expectation of the future; but if for some reason it moves to point B, the distance between point A to B becomes empty space (= vacuum) unless air or any other matter fills the space. Since any expectation of a latter time is the future, the distance between point A and B is the future at the time the movement of the object was taking place.

(nb Time = Distance/Speed)

Table of Contents

ABOUT	1
MY ANSWERS TO DIVISION BY ZERO QUESTIONS	3
What does the “not (0)” symbol mean?	3
What is the unification of zero?.....	4
Why is a number division by zero undefined? Doesn't zero mean "no"?	5
Can zero covid ever be achieved?	6
We have multiplication, division, addition, and subtraction. Is it possible to create a new one?	7
What is actually the difference between "a number divided by half" and "a number divided in half"?.....	9
When 3 divided by 3 is equal to 1, then if 0 divided by 0, what will the answer be?.....	9
What happens if you divide zero by zero?.....	10
Why is $5/0 = \text{error}$, and not 0?.....	11
What is $1 \div 0$?	13
How do you prove $x^0=1$?.....	16
Why is $0=2$?.....	17
In the derivation of remainder theorem, we divide $f(x)$ by $(x-a)$...What's wrong?	18
Why was Brahmagupta's system of division by zero given up on?	19
Why is $1/0$ undefined but $0/0$ indeterminate?	20
What does it mean when there is a zero in the denominator?	21
If two quantities have different dimensions, is it possible to multiply and or divide them?.....	22
Who stated that zero divided by any number equals zero?	23
What would happen if I try to divide by zero in my head?	24
What is the answer, if we divide zero by zero?.....	25
Is $1/\text{infinity}$ equal to 0?	25
What is $339354939934/0$?	27
If all numbers divided by themselves are 1, is $0/0=1$? Why or why not?	27
What is the result of 9 divided by 0?.....	28
REFERENCES	29

MY ANSWERS TO DIVISION BY ZERO QUESTIONS

1

What does the “not (0)” symbol mean?

Answered 21 March, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pGXYvg>

This is a brilliant question because it enables us understand the various definitions in mathematics used to denote zero. The symbol (\emptyset) is mainly used in set theory to denote zero. It's also called an empty set. In other words a “not (0)” or “ \emptyset ” **symbol simply means a zero in set theory**.

- In **set theory**, 0 is the **cardinality** of the **empty set**: if one does not have any apples, then one has 0 apples. In fact, in certain axiomatic developments of mathematics from set theory, 0 is **defined** to be the empty set. When this is done, the empty set is the **von Neumann cardinal assignment** for a set with no elements, which is the empty set. The cardinality function, applied to the empty set, returns the empty set as a value, thereby assigning it 0 elements. Wikipedia

See here

Zero [https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/0#Other branches of mathematics](https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/0#Other_branches_of_mathematics)

Take note that an empty set does not mean nothing because the set exists: The practical example given above to elaborate an empty set is “if one does not have any apples, then one has 0 apples.”

This is how you prove that **an empty set is not nothing**:

If you multiply two empty sets, you get 1 because of the multiplicative identity.

But if you multiply zero with zero, you don't get 1. If I multiply no apples with zero apples, surely I should get zero apples. This is not the case with set theory. See here

Empty product https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Empty_product

In simple terms, zero cannot be defined as nothing because **0^1 is not equal to 0^0** , see here

What happens if you divide zero by zero? <https://qr.ae/pN010E> (Page 10)

2

What is the unification of zero?

Answered 21 March, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pGXyYe>

The unification of zero is **the agreed definition(s) of zero across all branches of mathematics & sciences and it falls under the Unifying Theories in Mathematics**. It is this unification that helps define **what constitutes the numeral zero as the subject** across different disciplines in science & mathematics.

Since branches of mathematics and sciences keep making new discoveries, the definition of zero will keep growing in relation to those discoveries.

An example of a unique way to view division by zero is portrayed below:

The unification of zero falls under the **Unifying theories in mathematics**, see here

Unifying theories in mathematics

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unifying_theories_in_mathematics

3

Why is a number division by zero undefined? Doesn't zero mean "no"? After all, dividing a number by zero means not dividing it at all. I think $3:0 = 3$?

Answered: 17 March, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pNfuSw>

You are actually asking three questions in one:

1. **Why is a number division by zero undefined?**

If I am to be honest with you, undefined simply means '**no one has defined it yet**' hence undefined. In other words, mathematician understand division by zero in terms of what zero and division means but can't define the end result. That's why their answers range from infinity, NaN, Error all the way to indeterminate.

2. **Doesn't zero mean "no"?**

It depends what you mean by "no"

If by "no" you mean don't use zero then ' 0×0 ' would be undefined because we cannot use the zeros.

3. **Dividing a number by zero means not dividing it at all e.g. $3/0 = 3$.**

I must agree with you on this one because **there is a difference between $0/1$ and $0/0$** :

- $0/1$ means dividing by 1 i.e. **zero dividing by 1**
- $0/0$ means dividing by 0 i.e. **zero dividing by 0**
- Therefore **$0/1$ is not equal to $0/0$**
Or **0^1 is not equal to 0^0**
- **My point here is the meaning of zero (0^1) in the numerator is not the same as the meaning of zero (0^0) in the denominator.**

Zero (in the denominator) does not mean nothing, **see here:**

Can zero covid ever be achieved? <https://qr.ae/pNf1dq> (Page 6)

- **Zero in the denominator actually means nothing** (because you are dividing by zero not 1 as I elaborated earlier). To understand the intricacies of zero in division by zero, **see here:**

What happens if you divide zero by zero? <https://qr.ae/pN010E> (Page 10)

4

Can zero covid ever be achieved?

Answered 16 March, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pNf1dq>

If you are asking this question from a medical perspective then I don't think it is possible, though this is not my area of interest.

Having said this, it is important to note that in linguistics, zero means nothing. But in sciences, it can get a bit complicated.

Zero does not mean nothing in science that's why we have trivial and non-trivial zeros. It even gets more complicated like when we talk about the powers of zeros e.g. 0^0 is not equal to 0^1 .

So if you were to define zero as nothing, what about 0^0 and which among them is greater?

It even gets worse: If negative one is less than zero, then it must be nothing. If it is nothing, then how can you add nothing with another nothing and get a different nothing? e.g. $-1 + (-1) = -2$ but $0 > -2$, hence -2 is nothing in linguistics.

The best example is always a scientific one:

If you multiply 2 eggs by zero, you get zero i.e. $2 \times 0 = 0$

But if you multiply 2 eggs by nothing, you get 2 eggs because you did not multiply them with anything. Hence $2 \times 0 = 2$

But you may say, science is wrong to say that " $2 \times 0 = 0$ " instead of " $2 \times 0 = 2$ ". The answer to this is that science has never said (= proven) that zero is nothing. This is a misconception from linguistics because in science, you MUST prove or disapprove, period.

See here for more details about how complicated it can get.

Why is $0=2$? <https://qr.ae/pN01Sl> (Page 17)

The reason why it gets complicated is because in science, we deal with computations or calculations e.g. all scientific laws must be written using a mathematical method (i.e. using numbers) otherwise, they don't qualify as scientific laws.

But in linguistics, this is not necessary hence zero can be used to mean "zero in" which means investigate. "Zero in" has nothing to do with number zero in science, however it has something to do with zero in linguistics. I think you get the point.

In science it's all about proofs and disproofs. In linguistics, it's all about the art communication.

5

We have multiplication, division, addition, and subtraction. Is it possible to create a new one?

Answered 12 March, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN0p1P>

This is a very interesting question. I have a simple answer:

The Number line

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Number_line

All mathematical operations work as per the Number line.

For example, **Subtraction** means you go to the left, **Addition** means you go to the right. **Multiplication** and **Division** can go either way depending on whether the number is Positive or Negative.

So to answer your question, **we can create or de-create any operation except for Addition & Subtraction**: We cannot do without Addition and Subtraction because we will not be able to go **Right** or **Left** on the Number line.

In other words all operations are nothing but exaggerated/repeated Additions and Subtractions

Though this is the case, it is not always true for division by zero e.g.

$$8 \div 2 = ?$$

$$8 - 2 - 2 - 2 - 2 = 0.$$

I subtracted 8 by 2, four times,

$$\text{so } 8 \div 4 = 2.$$

$$8 \div 1 = ?$$

$$8 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 - 1 = 0.$$

I subtracted 8 by 1, eight times,

$$\text{so } 8 \div 8 = 1.$$

Hence

$$8 \div 0 = ?$$

$$8 - 0 - 0 - 0 - 0 - 0 - 0 - 0 \dots \neq 0$$

I am supposed to subtract 8 by 0, infinity times, right?

But **8 - 0 is not equal to 0**, hence **using infinity is futile** and useless since **the end result must be zero** yet $8 - 0 = 8$

As you can see, it seems we have reached a dead end.

But there is something we haven't tested yet:

There are two types of zeros:

$$0_1 = 0^1 = 0$$

$$0_0 = 0^0$$

NOTE $0_0 = 1_0$ see here:

What happens if you divide zero by zero? <https://qr.ae/pN010E>

Actually 0^0 is the 'right zero' to use because

$8 \div 0$ is equal to $8 \times (1_0)$ because $8_1 \times 1_0 = 8_0$ hence 0^0

$8 \div 0$ is not equal to $8 \times (0_1)$ because $8_1 \times 0_1 = 0_1$ hence 0^1

As rightly proven, **the problem was not with the calculation but with the use of the 'wrong zero.'**

Now let's do the same calculations but using the 'right zero'

$$8 \div 0 = ?$$

$$8 - 0^0 = 0$$

I subtracted 8 by 0^0 , 0^0 times (though it doesn't really matter how many times you subtract 0^0)

But what is 1/0 anyway? Luckily, there is a way of understanding 1/0 by use of a mathematical sequence e.g. what is the meaning of dividing an orange into 3 parts, 2 parts, 1 part hence zero part. To avoid repeating the same answer see here:

The analysis has been done here:

What is 1 ÷ 0? <https://qr.ae/pN01mH> (Page 13)

6

What is actually the difference between "a number divided by half" and "a number divided in half"?

Answered 12 March, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN0Tjk>

Say 1 is the number to be divided,

A number divided by half = $1 \div \frac{1}{2} = 1 \times 2 = 2$

A number divided in half = $1 \times \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{1} \times \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}$

P.S.

To get into a debate about the definition of division in the solving division by zero see here: [My Academic Review Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof](#)

7

When 3 divided by 3 is equal to 1, then if 0 divided by 0, what will the answer be?

Answered February 22, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN0T8n>

I assume you are enquiring if $0/0 = 1$ since any number divided by itself is 1, that is:

Since: $2/2 = 2^1 \div 2^1 = 2^{1-1} = 2^0 = 1$

Is: $0/0 = 0^1 \div 0^1 = 0^{1-1} = 0^0 = 1?$

The answer is NO. Zero divided by Zero does not equate to 1 as I explained here:

What is the proof of $a^0 = 1$? <https://qr.ae/pN0T8z> (Page 16)

My Academic Review Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof: <https://zenodo.org/record/4304933>

8

What happens if you divide zero by zero?

Answered February 22, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN010E>

In division, the denominator (divisor) determines the calculation outcome, for example:

$$1/2 = \mathbf{2 \text{ parts}} \text{ of } 1 = \mathbf{1/2} \times 1 = 1/2$$

$$2/2 = \mathbf{2 \text{ parts}} \text{ of } 2 = \mathbf{1/2} \times 2 = 2/2$$

$$\text{Hence } 0/0 = \mathbf{0 \text{ part}} \text{ of } 0 = \mathbf{1/0} \times 0 = 0/0$$

$$\mathbf{But } 1/0 \times 0 = \mathbf{1^1 \div 0^1 \times 0^1 = 1^1 \div 0^2}$$

$$1^1 \div 0^2 = 1^1 \div 0^1 = 1 \div 0$$

$$1 \div 0 = 1/0$$

$$\mathbf{Therefore } 0/0 = \mathbf{1/0} \text{ because } \mathbf{0^0 \neq 0^1}$$

$$\text{Or } 0/0 \neq 0/1$$

Now to answer your question: To solve $1/0$ you use a mathematical sequence, that is:

$1/3, 1/2, 1/1$ hence $1/0$ as I previously explained & demonstrated here:

What is $1 \div 0$? <https://qr.ae/pN01mH> (Page 13)

From this illustration, we can deduce the common denominator is division. I call it real division because it applies in reality. Real division can also be called separation. Separation cannot occur without movement as deduced from the sequence.

Therefore as shown from the illustrated sequence of real division, the answer to $1/0$ is VA. VA stands for Vacuum. Vacuum in mathematics is defined as absence of quantity.

Again I will use the sequence method to prove my definition: Say we have two quantities, one quantity, zero quantity, one negative quantity and so on.

Before I explain this, you may be tricked into thinking that Zero is VA. But as I mentioned in your previous question "why is $0=2$?" (link below), Zero can be equivalent to any number you wish, therefore it cannot be an absent quantity. Zero can represent any number as I explained in the said Quora forum here:

Why is $0=2$? <https://qr.ae/pN01SI> (Page 17)

Now that this has been cleared out, I will go back to the sequence but this time there will be no "zero quantity": We will have 3 quantities, 2 quantities, 1 quantity then an absent quantity (= VA)

One may argue that an absent quantity is not a quantity and therefore not a number. This is correct if you don't understand what vacuum is.

As I said earlier, VA in mathematics is absence of quantity because in mathematics we use quantities not matter.

Say I move a quantity from point A to B. Point A will be VA because the quantity is ABSENT in point A. Point A is also the PAST of point B because the object WAS (= Past) in point A and NOW (= Present) is in point B.

From this analysis we can deduce that VA is the Past of a quantity hence the Past of a number.

Therefore since the PRESENT is a calculation of the PAST, then the PAST can be calculated.

Therefore VA is a SIGN that represents PAST quantities but not representing PRESENT quantities. Numbers are SIGNS that represent PRESENT quantities (e.g PRESENT quantity = 1) hence VA is a number as well (e.g PAST Quantity = $1/0$ or VA)

I have left some links in this PDF paper if you may wish to delve deeper into this and analyze how to calculate VA (e.g. $VA + 1 = ?$) or how to interpret $0/0$. Please download this PDF paper and understand it first because it's the basis of my solution.

<https://zenodo.org/record/4304933>

DIVISION BY ZERO CAN BE SOLVED.

9

Why is $5/0 = \text{error}$, and not 0? Let's say that have five apples that we want to divide on a non-existent human. Since that human doesn't exist, shouldn't he have zero apples?

Answered February 21, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN016E>

Firstly let's be clear, this type of analogy of the description of division is false: You have 5 apples, and you have humans. There's is no common denominator. This is because it relates (= relative) to both apples and humans. In other words, you cannot divide unlike terms in mathematics e.g. $y/y=1$

but $y/z \neq 1$ (where $y \neq z$) hence you cannot divide apples in relation to humans, instead you divide them in relation to themselves, that is, the apples.

But if you do the latter, the statement will not make sense e.g. If you share an apple among 2 apples ($= a/2a$), how many apples will each apple get? ($= 1/2$) a^2

Note: $a = 1$ apple

This is the correct mathematical statement because " $a/2a = (1/2) a^2$ " but even though it's correct, it doesn't make sense. This leads to mathematical conjectures (= educated guess work) that has nothing to do with mathematics; that is, it's acceptable to assume that even though the apples are being given to humans, they remain apples. This seems correct until you realize the equation would then have to look like this: " $(a/2a) + 2h$ " where h =human.

Now that this is clear, let's attempt to solve the problem mathematically without the "h" factor.

$5/0$ means 5 divided into zero parts; not $(5/0) + h$

To understand or analyze what $5/0$ means, we will have to deduce or make comparisons with similar calculations: What do these calculations mean: $1/3$, $1/2$, $1/1(=5/5)$ and finally $1/0$?

To understand this mathematical sequence in a clear and precise way, please review my answer on a previously asked question regarding division by zero **here**:

What is $1 \div 0$? <https://qr.ae/pN01mH> (Page 13)

From this illustration, we can deduce the common denominator is division. I call it real division because it applies in reality. Real division can also be called separation. Separation cannot occur without movement as deduced from the sequence.

Therefore as shown from the illustrated sequence of real division, the answer to $1/0$ is VA. VA stands for Vacuum. Vacuum in mathematics is defined as absence of quantity.

Again I will use the sequence method to prove my definition: Say we have two quantities, one quantity, zero quantity, one negative quantity and so on.

Before I explain this, you may be tricked into thinking that Zero is VA. But as I mentioned in your previous question "why is $0=2$?" (link below), Zero can be equivalent to any number you wish, therefore it cannot be an absent quantity. Zero can represent any number as I explained in the said Quora forum here:

Why is $0=2$? <https://qr.ae/pN01SI> (Page 17)

Now that this has been cleared out, I will go back to the sequence but this time there will be no "zero quantity": We will have 3 quantities, 2 quantities, 1 quantity then an absent quantity (= VA)

One may argue that an absent quantity is not a quantity and therefore not a number. This is correct if you don't understand what vacuum is.

As I said earlier, VA in mathematics is absence of quantity because in mathematics we use quantities not matter.

Say I move a quantity from point A to B. Point A will be VA because the quantity is ABSENT in point A. Point A is also the PAST of point B because the object WAS (= Past) in point A and NOW (= Present) is in point B.

From this analysis we can deduce that VA is the Past of a quantity hence the Past of a number.

Therefore since the PRESENT is a calculation of the PAST, then the PAST can be calculated.

Therefore VA is a SIGN that represents PAST quantities but not representing PRESENT quantities. Numbers are SIGNS that represent PRESENT quantities (e.g. PRESENT quantity = 1) hence VA is a number as well (e.g. PAST Quantity = $1/0$ or VA)

I have left some links in this PDF paper if you may wish to delve deeper into this and analyze how to calculate VA (e.g. $VA + 1 = ?$) or how to interpret $0/0$. Please download this PDF paper and understand it first because it's the basis of my solution.

<https://zenodo.org/record/4304933>

10

What is $1 \div 0$?

Answered February 14, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01mH>

Originally Answered: What is your answer to $1/0$?

I am glad you asked "what is (or answer to) $1/0$?" instead of "what is the calculation for $1/0$?"

The difference between the two is that the first question has to do with the qualities of $1/0$ while the latter has to do with calculations based on conjectures.

Any sound mathematician will never solve a mathematical problem without first understanding the characteristics of a calculation. I call this analytical mathematics.

So to answer your question, we will need to compare what we don't know with what is already known. We call this deduction.

To deduce $1/0$, we need to first deduce $1/3$, $1/2$, $1/1$ and then finally we will be able to understand $1/0$.

This type of deduction is called a sequence.

Deduction is part of both Applied Mathematics & Pure Mathematics because of the sequence characteristic. No one has ever been successful in giving us a reliable answer to $1/0$ but now it's possible:

DIVISION BY ZERO SOLUTION

("Vacuum Calculation Burden of Proof" PDF papers)

Scientific Method Used: A Sequence Mathematical Method from $1/3$ to $1/0$

Figure showing Division of a Quantity

1	$=$	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">Quantity</div>		
$\frac{1}{3}$	$=$	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">$\frac{1}{3}$</div> \leftrightarrow <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">$\frac{1}{3}$</div> \leftrightarrow <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">$\frac{1}{3}$</div>	\rightarrow	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">$\leftrightarrow =$ Separation or Movement</div>
$\frac{1}{2}$	$=$	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">$\frac{1}{2}$</div> \leftrightarrow <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">$\frac{1}{2}$</div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center; color: green;">Division cannot occur without Separation (=Movement)</div>
$\frac{1}{1}$	$=$	<div style="border: 1px dashed black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">VA</div> \leftrightarrow <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">1</div>	\rightarrow	<div style="text-align: center;">(Note the difference between $\frac{1}{1}$ & 1)</div> <div style="text-align: center;"> ➔ The difference is in the Separation <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block; margin-top: 5px;">The Movement leaves an empty space (= VA)</div> </div>
$\frac{1}{0}$	$=$	<div style="border: 1px dashed black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">VA</div> \leftrightarrow <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;">1</div>		

The denominator determines the number of parts of the object.

Thus:

- $\frac{1}{3}$ determines the 3 parts
- $\frac{1}{2}$ determines the 2 parts
- $\frac{1}{1}$ determines the 1 part

Hence:

- $\frac{1}{0}$ determines the absence of quantity (= Vacuum) part or Past of quantity

Please share this with friends

From this illustration, we can deduce the common denominator is division. I call it real division because it applies in reality. Real division can also be called separation. Separation cannot occur without movement as deduced from the sequence.

Therefore as shown from the illustrated sequence of real division, the answer to $1/0$ is VA. VA stands for Vacuum. Vacuum in mathematics is defined as absence of quantity.

Again I will use the sequence method to prove my definition: Say we have two quantities, one quantity, zero quantity, one negative quantity and so on.

Before I explain this, you may be tricked into thinking that Zero is VA. But as I mentioned in your previous question "why is $0=2$?" (link below), Zero can be equivalent to any number you wish, therefore it cannot be an absent quantity. Zero can represent any number as I explained in the said quora forum here:

Link: Why is $0=2$? <https://qr.ae/pN01SI> (Page 17)

Now that this has been cleared out, I will go back to the sequence but this time there will be no "zero quantity": We will have 3 quantities, 2 quantities, 1 quantity then an absent quantity (= VA)

One may argue that an absent quantity is not a quantity and therefore not a number. This is correct if you don't understand what vacuum is.

As I said earlier, VA in mathematics is absence of quantity because in mathematics we use quantities not matter.

Say I move a quantity from point A to B. Point A will be VA because the quantity is ABSENT in point A. Point A is also the PAST of point B because the object WAS (= Past) in point A and NOW (= Present) is in point B.

From this analysis we can deduce that VA is the Past of a quantity hence the Past of a number.

Therefore since the PRESENT is a calculation of the PAST, then the PAST can be calculated.

Therefore VA is a SIGN that represents PAST quantities but not representing PRESENT quantities. Numbers are SIGNS that represent PRESENT quantities (e.g. PRESENT quantity = 1) hence VA is a number as well (e.g. PAST Quantity = $1/0$ or VA)

I have left some links in this PDF paper if you may wish to delve deeper into this and analyze how to calculate VA (e.g. $VA + 1 = ?$) or how to interpret $0/0$. Please download this PDF paper and understand it first because it's the basis of my solution.

Link: [My Academic Review Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof](#)

11

How do you prove $x^0=1$?

Answered February 14, 2021

Originally Answered: How do you write the mathematical proof that any number to the zero power is 1?

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01Jl>

The reason why zero to the power of zero is not 1

Quora.com/David Kathuri

Mathematical Proof that Zero to the Power of Zero is not 1

$$\frac{3}{3} = \frac{3^1}{3^1} = 3^{1-1} = 3^0 = 1 \quad \text{because} \quad \frac{3}{3} = 1$$

$$\frac{2}{2} = \frac{2^1}{2^1} = 2^{1-1} = 2^0 = 1 \quad \text{because} \quad \frac{2}{2} = 1$$

$$\frac{1}{1} = \frac{1^1}{1^1} = 1^{1-1} = 1^0 = 1 \quad \text{because} \quad \frac{1}{1} = 1$$

$$\frac{0}{0} = \frac{0^1}{0^1} = 0^{1-1} = 0^0 = 1 \quad \text{but} \quad \frac{0}{0} \neq 1$$

Hence $0^0 \neq 1$

Reason: Zero is Positive & Negative at the same time,
that is: $-0 = +0 = \pm 0$

Mathematical Proof

$$\frac{3}{3} = \frac{3^1}{3^1} = 3^{1-1} = 3^0 = 1$$

$$\frac{-3}{+3} = \frac{-3^1}{+3^1} = -3^{1-1} = -3^0 = 1 \quad \text{but} \quad \frac{-3}{+3} \neq 1$$

Since $\frac{-3}{+3} \neq 1$ **then** $\frac{-0}{+0} \neq 1$

Hence $\frac{\pm 0}{\pm 0} \neq 1$

For more info on the **solution for division by zero** go to:

<https://zenodo.org/record/4304933>

Link: <https://zenodo.org/record/4304933>

12

Why is $0=2$?

Answered February 11, 2021

Originally Answered: Why does $0=2$?

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01SI>

The best approach is to define zero via calculations rather than conjectures.

If we add 1 by 1, we get two. In the same way, if we take away 1 from 1, we get zero.

This sounds correct until we analyze it using a scientific method (= practically).

Say we add an orange to another orange, we get 2 oranges. In the same way, if we take away an orange from another orange we get zero orange, right? Wrong:

We originally started with 2 oranges, we took away only one orange. Hence we remain with one orange because we had 2 oranges to start with.

If you don't believe it, try it practically (= scientifically).

(Note: In mathematics we cannot calculate a single unit. The units must be two or more. In this context, we cannot subtract one orange from itself because all operators (such as addition, subtraction, division & multiplication) require at least two units e.g. $1+1$ not $1+?$)

Therefore $1 - (+1) = 1$ hence $0 = 1$

Thus $2 - (+2) = 2$ hence $0 = 2$

From a scientific (as above) and mathematical perspective, we can prove that $0=2$. But if this was allowed, mathematics would lose meaning because any number will be equal to any other number.

The problem with $0=2$ has to do with Division by Zero. This problem is solved by defining Division by Zero. It's possible to define Division by zero via science and applied mathematics. This proof enables us understand why $0=2$. Division by zero can be easily proven as the past (or future) of a given number. For example zero can be equal to 2 depending on how it's calculated in its future. Therefore $0=2$ (when division by zero is involved). NOTE: It's impossible to come up with " $0=2$ " without having divided by zero in the first place. You can try it out if you have a contrary opinion.

For further information on how to SOLVE DIVISION BY ZERO download this PDF document paper because it contains all information required to start your journey on a firm and concrete premise:

[My Academic Review Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof.pdf](#)

13

In the derivation of remainder theorem, we divide $f(x)$ by $(x-a)$ where $x=a$. But $(x-a)$ is just $(a-a)$ which is zero. But anything divided by 0 is infinite, forcing us to conclude that $f(x)$ is infinite which is wrong. What's wrong?

Answered February 11, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01cY>

What's wrong has to do with the meaning of polynomial. The question is based on the wrong premise because the Remainder Theorem is a polynomial. "In mathematics, a polynomial is an expression consisting of variables (also called indeterminates) and coefficients, that involves only the operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and non-negative integer exponentiation of variables." source Wikipedia

Polynomial <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polynomial>

Hence division is not required.

Secondly, you say anything divided by zero is infinite. Though not directly related to this question, I would like to share my thoughts on this:

Say that a number (e.g. 1) divided by zero is possible, where the denominator (or divisor) is a number that's approaching zero hence will eventually reach zero. Therefore 1 divided by zero is infinity.

This holds until you realize that any number that's not zero cannot be positive and negative at the same time i.e. \pm (no matter how close it approaches ± 0) e.g. $+1=+1$ not ± 1 but $\pm 0=\pm 0$

With this analysis it's very easy to make a firm & concrete analysis that a negative or positive number (other than zero) will never be equal to " \pm " number (no matter how close it approaches \pm) because a negative or positive number in division will remain so and can never equate to ' \pm ' number hence Infinity is not a mathematical number. It's the same as saying a blue number, pink number and then trying to add them together while expecting a valid mathematical solution.

In simple terms, if you have oranges (or any other quantity) approaching infinity, they don't cease to be oranges just because you included the word Infinity to them. They will remain oranges no matter how infinite you wish them to become. It is the counting that may be limited to our ability to count them.

14

Why was Brahmagupta's system of division by zero given up on?

Answered January 29, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01aI>

Firstly, we need to analyze the said Brahmagupta's system

"A positive or negative number when divided by zero is a fraction with the zero as denominator."

"Zero divided by a negative or positive number is either zero or is expressed as a fraction with zero as numerator and the finite quantity as denominator."

"Zero divided by zero is zero."

In the first case, he only asserts or recognizes that division by zero is a fraction. Therefore, in my view he is correct in his assertions.

In the second case, he is asserting the reciprocal of division by zero. In my view, his assertion is acceptable.

In the third case, he is actually claiming to solve the division by zero problem. This is where his solution (not system) was rejected (but not necessarily given up on) because it leads to this:

It is true that $0/0=0$ but it's also true $0/0=1,2,3...$

When $y=1$ & $y=2$ means $1=2$

If $1=2$ then every number can be equal any other number.

The question here is, is this possible? ($1=2$)

Most mathematicians would say it's not possible because it would make counting using numbers useless.

This is true, only if, numbers ignore the possibility of TIME in counting numbers. For example, the numeral 1 can be the numeral 2 in the Future, depending on how it's calculated in its Future.

The best practical example to understand this is by evaluating how our brains analyzes objects. For instance, a person with 2 eyes observing an orange will not see 2 oranges even though he has 2 eyes. This is because our brain understands Brahmagupta's system. Even though our 2 eyes should see 2 oranges ($2=2$) rather than one ($2=1$), our brains are intelligent enough to understand that some-times, $2=1$.

The science that explains this is simple and doable. It's under the topic "CONDUIT LOGIC" In the paper: VACUUM CALCULATIONS BURDEN OF PROOF. You will find the download link and other information in this PDF document: [My Academic Review Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof.pdf](#)

Sorry but I cannot explain it all here but it involves how Time affects numbers. If you are interested on HOW TO SOLVE DIVISION BY ZERO please download the above PDF doc. IT'S POSSIBLE TO DIVIDE BY ZERO.

15

Why is $1/0$ undefined but $0/0$ indeterminate?

Answered January 21, 2021

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01UK>

Answering original question: Why is it concluded that zero divided by itself is undefined when a similar $1/1$ is 1 and $1/0$ is 0?

First of all let's be clear: Conclusions made on something undefined are baseless and mundane. In other words, conclusions are based on scientifically sound discoveries but not on conjectures that rely on educated guess work. In layman's terms, If you see a conclusion that's undefined, then it's an undefined conclusion.

Secondly, division in mathematics does not mean multiplicative inverse, it simply means counting or computing. This is the case for all operators in Mathematics. For example you compute or count numbers by adding, subtracting, dividing and so on.

The multiplicative inverse does not compute anything, it simply rearranges the calculation.

E.g. $1/0 = (1/0)$ therefore $(1/0) \times 0 = 1$. As you can see from this rearrangement, it's possible to conclude that multiplying zero with $1/0$ can accurately and definitively give us the answer "1". But this is not the case.

Division simply means separation NOT multiplicative inverse. For example, $1/2$ means 1 separated into 2 equal parts. This can be proven scientifically as the meaning of Division by dividing one quantity (e.g. an orange) into two parts.

Thirdly, you are correct in saying: the calculation $1/1$ and $1/0$ are similar (though $1/0 \neq 0$).

You are correct because if you practically (=scientifically) divide an orange into 1 part, you will remain with the 1 part. In the same way, if you divide an orange into zero parts, then you haven't divided the orange at all, hence you'll still remain with the same orange.

Therefore one would assume $(1/0) \times 0 = 1$ as we saw earlier (when I explained the meaning of the multiplicative inverse).

That is correct, but division means separation and separation means movement.

If I explain what I mean by movement, it would be off topic and make my answer too long, therefore follow this link if you are curious enough: [David Kathuri's share of "My Academic Review Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof" in Division by Zero](#)

I assure you IT'S SCIENTIFICALLY (=PRACTICALLY) POSSIBLE TO DIVIDE BY ZERO.

16

What does it mean when there is a zero in the denominator?

Answered December 17, 2020

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01gn>

The best way to tackle this question is to ask 'what does it mean when there is a 1 or 2 in the denominator?'

When we have a 2 in the denominator, it means the numerator must be divided into 2 parts.

When we have a 1 in the denominator, it means the numerator must be divided into 1 parts.

Therefore when we have a 0 in the denominator, it means the numerator must be divided into 0 parts.

But I am sure you already know this. I assume therefore that what you are actually asking is whether there is any significance in dividing by zero.

To understand the significance or importance of any mathematical problem, we apply it in a physical context.

So for instance, what does it mean to divide an orange into zero parts?

Again, the best way to solve this is to find out what it means to divide by 1 or 2 and so on.

If it is by 2, the orange must be divided into 2 parts. If it is by 1, the orange must be divided into 1 part. Therefore if it is by zero, the orange must be divided into zero parts.

Therefore, we may ask: What does it mean to divide an orange into zero parts? This is a very interesting but tricky question. I had answered this question here: [David Kathuri's answer to What is the answer, if we divide zero by zero?](#)

17

If two quantities have different dimensions, is it possible to multiply and or divide them? Can we add and or subtract them for O level?

Answered November 19, 2020

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01w9>

Think about this question – can you add 1meter to $1m^2$ & $1m^3$? That is: $1m+1m^2+1m^3=?$

I'll refer to Length, area and volume: adding - Dimensional analysis - Intermediate & Higher tier - WJEC - GCSE Maths Numeracy (WJEC) Revision - BBC Bitesize

“Think about this question – can you add a length to an area?

Hopefully you have come to the conclusion that this is in fact impossible. The reason for this is that length and area have different units, and quantities with different units cannot be added together.

This also explains why we cannot add a time to a weight or why we cannot simplify $3a + 2b$, as the answer would be nonsense!

One final consideration is that we cannot add or subtract dimensionless quantities (normal numbers such as 5, 12.8 and 34) to a quantity with dimensions.

While quantities with different units cannot be added – they can often be multiplied.” (End of ref.)

So here are some of the simplest possible scenarios for your question:

$$m+m^2+m^3=?$$

$$m-m^2-m^3=?$$

$$m\times m^2\times m^3=?$$

$$m\div m^2 ; m^2\div m^3=? \text{ and so on}$$

You get answers depending on your solution method i.e. how you define or explain your solution.

18

Who stated that zero divided by any number equals zero?

Answered November 4, 2020

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01Mh>

I would give it to Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta. An indian. Before his time, it was thought that zero cannot be a number. Numbers began at 'greater than zero' >0 .

This reference is from [\(Division by zero - Wikipedia\)](#)

EARLY ATTEMPTS:

The Brāhmasphuṭasiddhānta of Brahmagupta (c. 598–668) is the earliest text to treat zero as a number in its own right and to define operations involving zero.

The author could not explain division by zero in his texts: his definition can be easily proven to lead to algebraic absurdities. According to Brahmagupta,

"A positive or negative number when divided by zero is a fraction with the zero as denominator. Zero divided by a negative or positive number is either zero or is expressed as a fraction with zero as numerator and the finite quantity as denominator. Zero divided by zero is zero."

In 830, Mahāvīra unsuccessfully tried to correct Brahmagupta's mistake in his book in Ganita Sara Samgraha: "A number remains unchanged when divided by zero." (Division by zero - Wikipedia)

19

What would happen if I try to divide by zero in my head?

Answered November 4, 2020

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01k8>

Your question is very interesting because it depends on who you ask:

If you ask a mathematician or scientists, you'll get an accurate but not a reasonable answer. He would reply, "all calculations are done 'inside my head' including division by zero. I then write them down as I desire, probably on a piece of paper. Without my head I wouldn't calculate simple mathematics like $1+1$."

But if you ask a psychiatrist, you'll get a realistic answer. He would reply, "the answer is within you, and if it's not, it's somewhere out there waiting to be discovered."

If you ask a philosopher then you'll get a more reasonable but not an accurate answer. He would reply, "to get to the bottom of this, we would have to make some comparisons: What is the difference between 'dividing by zero in your head' and 'dividing the same outside of your head'? You could, without doubt, get only two results: Inside your head, I am not certain; but outside your head, a mad man."

To answer your question, the psychiatrist is right. The answer is solved via a discovery, just like other unknown mathematical problems. This is because you can't tell what would happen if what would happen is unknown.

See my page for more info on division by zero.

20

What is the answer, if we divide zero by zero?

Answered October 28, 2020

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01PY>

Originally Answered: What can actually be divided by zero?

First of all, the question 'What can actually be divided by zero?' defers from the question "What is the result (or outcome) of division by zero?"

So to answer your question, nothing can be divided by zero in the same way nothing can be divided by one.

For example, if I divide an orange into zero parts, I will end up with the same orange. In the same breath, if I divide the orange into one part, I will end up with the same orange.

The real quagmire lies on the exact meaning of division, that is, 'what does it mean to divide?' rather than "what can actually be divided?"

'What does it mean to divide' refers to the laws or axioms of division. They are determined by the denominator in a fraction setting.

'What can actually be divided' refers to the application of the laws or axioms of division. They are determined by the numerator of a fraction.

I have my own tangible explanation of division by zero. Please visit my page for more info.

21

Is $1/\infty$ equal to 0?

Answered May 29, 2020

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01oz>

To answer this question we would first have to define the term infinity.

Infinity (often denoted by the symbol ∞) represents something that is boundless or endless or else something that is larger than any real or natural number. (Wikipedia)

Let's assume the largest number in the universe is 10, which would mean 11 must be infinity, right?

No, because 11 is quantifiable. Well since 11 has failed our test, how about 12. That must surely be infinity since it's beyond quantifiability, right?

Well, a new term has emerged: 'quantifiability'. So let's check it out...

Quantifiability stems from the word quantity:

Quantity is a property that can exist as a multitude or magnitude, which illustrate discontinuity and continuity. (Wikipedia)

Hmm... discontinuity & continuity are the key words.

Does infinity has a beginning (= property of continuity)? No. How about an end (= property of discontinuity)?, No.

Hence infinity is beyond quantifiability (like say: blue + red = purple),

It is also beyond continuity & discontinuity (like say: blue + red = colour) - Colour is not necessarily blue or red. It could be pink, yellow etc. hence it has lost its continuity (= blue + red) & discontinuity (= purple).

Hence: Continuity + Discontinuity = Number

But: Continuity + Discontinuity \neq Infinity

Therefore: Number \neq Infinity

Therefore infinity is best described as the state of a number that cannot continue (as a quantity) or discontinue (as a quantity).

So to answer your question: is $1/\text{infinity}$ equal to 0?

My simple answer is infinity is not a number hence cannot be divided or divide.

P.S. If you wish to delve deeper into this, then studying my work is a must:

or read/download [Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof](#).

22

What is $339354939934/0$?

Answered May 28, 2020

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01Ab>

Thank you John for the interesting question. Please let me know why you chose this specific long number. Is there a specific reason or we could use the numeral '1' instead of '339354939934'?

That is: if 1 & 339354939934 are Positive numbers then $1, 339354939934 = P$

Hence 1 or 339354939934 divided by zero = $P/0$

23

If all numbers divided by themselves are 1, is $0/0=1$? Why or why not?

Answered March 17, 2020

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01rH>

That's a very good question. First of all let's define a number: A number is a mathematical object used to count, measure, and label (Wikipedia). So the real question is: Is zero a mathematical object?

The simple answer is yes. But wait a minute; what's the difference between $+0$ & -0 ?

Now, that's the problem:

If I decide to solve your question via the sequence method then:

$$3/3 = 1,$$

$$2/2 = 1,$$

$$1/1 = 1,$$

Hence:

$$0/0 = 1$$

This sounds correct, right?

Not until you realize that this object (zero) is both positive and negative at the same time that is ± 0 .

In simple terms, if the above sequence would apply to both positive & negative numbers, then you would have "hit the jackpot":

$$-3/-3 \neq -1,$$

$$-2/-2 \neq -1,$$

$$-1/-1 \neq -1,$$

Hence:

$$-0/-0 \neq -1,$$

Therefore:

$$\pm 0/\pm 0 \neq \pm 1,$$

That is: $0/0$ is not equal to negative one, hence cannot be equal to positive one (considering zero can either be positive or negative which is not the case for other numbers in the number line).

P.S. If you wish to delve deeper into this, then studying my work is a must: Mathematics of Division by Zero or read Vacuum Calculations Burden of Proof

Thank you.

24

What is the result of 9 divided by 0?

Answered October 18, 2019

Link: <https://qr.ae/pN01h5>

Originally Answered: What is 9 divided by 0?

Vacuum, yes that's what I said. Vacuum can be perfectly be defined as a number i.e. Numbers (in Applied Mathematics) are nothing but signs that represent quantities e.g an apple & another apple can be defined as 2. Therefore since absence of the quantities is defined as Vacuum then it can be defined as a number forthwith. (<https://youtu.be/h1ySUhznPos>)

REFERENCES

<https://www.quora.com/profile/David-Kathuri>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4304933>